

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

SURFACE LAYER OF GRAPHITE OXIDE

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Abstract

According to modern ideas, the surface layer is an ultra -thin film located in thermodynamic equilibrium with the volume of the rest of the crystal. The thickness of this film was experimentally learned to measure at the end of the twentieth century in a superhigh vacuum and only at the beginning of the 21st century was an empirical model of the thickness of the surface layer of solid bodies and even liquids was proposed. It turned out to be equal: 1-8 Nm for pure metals; 10-40 nm for fire crystals; 40-120 Nm for fullerenes, coal and polymers. The purpose of this article is to determine the surface layer of crystals of graphite oxide and graphene oxide and compare them with graphite and graphene. It is shown that the thickness of the surface layer in all graphene structures does not exceed 10 nm, i.e. they are nanostructure, at least in the plane z. A comparison of graphene structures showed their insignificant difference from the unique properties of the original graphene.

Keywords: graphite, graphene, graphite oxide, graphene oxide, surface layer, luminescence, crystal, energy, deformation, spectrum, emission.

Introduction

Graphite oxide (or graphene oxide) (GO) is a unique material that still retains the integrity and partly crystalline structure of the original two-dimensional graphene sheet, but, unlike the latter, has increased reactivity. The history of the discovery of GO and the latest achievements in its practical use can be read in the latest doctoral dissertations [1, 2].

The purpose of the article is to determine the surface layer of graphite oxide and graphene oxide crystals and compare them with graphite and graphene.

Graphite oxide and graphene oxide (a brief overview)

Graphene oxide is a berthollide, i.e. a compound of variable composition that changes depending on the method and conditions of production, in connection with which various structural models of GO have historically been presented (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. - Structural models of graphene oxide: a) Hoffman model; b) Ress model; c) Scholz-Boehm model; d) Dekaney model; e) Nakajima-Matsuo model; f) Lerf-Klinovsky model [1].

In [3], a comparison was made between the experimental infrared absorption spectrum of the synthesized GO sample and the spectra of model systems $C_nO_mH_k$ calculated using ab initio approaches, including the basic fragment of the graphite layer C_{54} and various functional groups modifying it (hydroxyl, epoxy, car-

boxyl and keto groups) in different quantities and combinations in the presence of a small number of solvating water molecules, the IR spectrum region of GO and to identify the role of hydrogen bonding between various functional groups and water molecules. The results are shown in Figs. 2 - 6.

Figure 2. - The structure of the model system $C_{54}H_{18}O_3$ and its calculated absorption spectrum in the range of $2000-500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [3].

Figure 3. - Structure of the model system $C_{54}H_{18}(OH)_8$ and its calculated absorption spectrum in the range of $2000-500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [3].

Figure 4. - The structure of the model system $C_{54}H_{18}O_3(OH)_6$ and its calculated absorption spectrum in the range of $2000-500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [3].

Figure 5. - Structure of the model system $C_{54}H_8O_2(OH)_{14}(H_2O)$ and its calculated absorption spectrum in the range of $2000\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [3].

Figure 6. - Structure of the model system $C_{54}H_{10}O(OH)_5(COOH)_5$ and its calculated absorption spectrum in the range of $2000\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [3].

Quantum-chemical modeling of the $C_nH_p(O)_k(OH)_l(COOH)_m$ systems, carried out in work [3], simulating the structure of local fragments of an oxidized graphite sheet, including epoxy and hydroxyl groups in its inner part and hydroxyl, carboxyl and keto groups at the boundary, made it possible to clarify the nature of most of the signals in the experimental absorption spectrum of graphite oxide in its middle and characteristic regions. In the characteristic region of the spectrum, the peak in the vicinity of 980 cm^{-1} cannot be due to the excitation of vibrations of individual epoxy groups. A noticeable contribution to this signal is made by deformation vibrations of hydroxyl groups located on the inner part of the carbon sheet, which are strongly associated with distortions of the corresponding C_4 pyramids.

Near 1100 cm^{-1} , the excitation of breathing vibrations of the unoxidized carbon framework and the distortion of peripheral hydroxyl groups initiated by it can manifest itself. The signal with the peak at 1370 cm^{-1} should receive a noticeable contribution from the deformation vibrations of the $C\text{--}O\text{--}H$ fragments of the carboxyl groups, interacting with the stretching vibrations of the corresponding $C\text{--}C(O)(OH)$ bonds and distortions of the carbon framework, both local (individual $C=C$ bonds) and covering relatively large areas of the

unoxidized carbon surface. In the middle region of the spectrum, the peak at 1615 cm^{-1} is due to the stretching vibrations of the carbon–carbon bonds, but its greater intensity is due to the conjugated stretching vibrations of the $C=O$ fragments and the deformation of the H-bonded hydroxyl groups. In the absence of carbonyl fragments in the system, the signal in this region of the spectrum has a very low intensity. The integral absorption at higher frequencies (peak at 1733 cm^{-1}) is provided by vibrations of carboxyl groups, which can be represented by a superposition of stretching of the $C=O$ bond and a change in the $C\text{--}O\text{--}H$ angle.

The chemical composition of graphene oxide and oxygen-containing functional groups can be determined using such spectroscopic methods of analysis as Raman spectroscopy, infrared spectroscopy (IR) (see above), solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) [1-3].

NMR spectra show that the main lines in the spectrum of graphene oxide correspond to: a peak at about 60 ppm to carbon atoms associated with epoxy functional groups; a peak at about 70 ppm corresponds to carbon atoms associated with hydroxyl groups; a peak at about 130 ppm refers to sp^2 -carbon atoms. Three more peaks at 101, 167 and 191 ppm are determined for lactone, carbonyl and ketone groups (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. - NMR spectrum of graphene oxide [4]

XPS reveals the nature of carbon and oxygen bonds in their various states: unoxidized carbon atoms (sp^2 -carbon), C-O-C, C=O and COOH. The C1s signal of OG (Fig. 8) consists of five different chemical components that can be transformed into sp^2 -carbon atoms

(284.5 eV) and carbon atoms associated with hydroxyl (C-OH, 285.86 eV), epoxy (C-O-C, 286.55 eV), carbonyl (C=O, 287.5 eV) and carboxyl groups (COOH, 289.2 eV).

Figure 8. - XPS spectrum of graphene oxide [5]

The Raman spectrum of GO displays a broad G-peak at 1580 cm^{-1} , which is characteristic of all sp^2 -hybridized carbon. In addition, the Raman spectrum contains D, Dr and D+G bands at 1330 cm^{-1} , 1620 cm^{-1} and 2915 cm^{-1} , which arise from structural defects (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. - Raman spectra of graphene oxide: a) depending on the type of reducing agent [6]; b) depending on the reduction temperature [5]

In Fig. 10, the size of GO depending on the time of ultrasonic treatment of the GO dispersion, which lasted for 2 and 16 hours.

Fig. 10. - Micrographs of graphene oxide flakes [7]

Surface layer of graphite oxide and graphene oxide

J. Gibbs represented the surface of a solid as a geometric plane with no thickness [8]. However, van der Waals [9] and Guggenheim [10] considered the surface layer as a layer of finite thickness, the size of which was empirically determined in [11]. According to modern

concepts, the surface layer is an ultrathin film in thermodynamic equilibrium with the volume of the rest of the crystal [12]. Experimentally, they learned to measure the thickness of this film at the end of the twentieth century in ultra-high vacuum using the sliding X-ray/synchrotron beam method (for example, the layer thickness for silicon was found to be 3.2 nm, and for gold – 1.2 nm) [13].

We first determined the thickness of the surface layer of graphite and graphene in [14-17] (Fig. 11a). In Fig. 11b shows the corrugations on the graphene surface. The thickness of the surface layer R(I) is given by the formula [14]:

$$R(I) = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \alpha \cdot \upsilon \text{ [m]}. \quad (1)$$

Figure 11. - Scheme of a solid: nanolayer → mesolayer → bulk phase (a); corrugated graphene (b)

In [16] it is shown that the surface energy of a bulk metal γ_2 with an accuracy of 3% is equal to:

$$\gamma_2 = 0,7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T_m \text{ [J/m}^2\text{]}, \quad (2)$$

where T_m is the melting temperature of the metal (K).

In the R(I) layer, the size effect must be taken into account and the surface energy becomes equal to γ_1 [17]:

$$\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 (1 - R(I)/R(I) + h) \approx 0,5\gamma_2, \quad (3)$$

where $\gamma_{12} = 0$ due to the second-order phase transition.

In equation (1) you need to know one parameter – the molar volume of the element, which is equal to $\upsilon = M/\rho$ (M is the molar mass, ρ is its density), $\alpha = 1 \text{ mol m}^{-2}$ is a constant to maintain the dimensionality ($R(I)$ [m]).

To separate the R(I) layer from the rest of the crystal, energy must be expended, which is called the specific adhesion energy:

$$W_a = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - \gamma_{12} \approx \gamma_1 + \gamma_2. \quad (4)$$

We calculate the internal stresses σ_{is} between phases γ_1 and γ_2 using the formula:

$$\sigma_{is} = \sqrt{W_a \cdot \dot{L} / R(I)}, \quad (5)$$

where E is the Young's modulus of elasticity.

In [18-20], it is shown that there are four forms of graphene products, namely: graphene (G), graphene oxide (GO), reduced graphene oxide (rGO), and graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs), as shown in Fig. 12.

Figure 12. – Image of (a) graphene (G), (b) graphene oxide (GO), (c) reduced graphene oxide (rGO), and (d) graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs)

Using (1), we calculate the parameters of graphite (Gr), graphene (G), graphite oxide (GrO), graphene oxide (GO) (Table 1).

Table 1.

Surface layer thickness R(I) of graphene structures						
Carbon	M, g/mol	ρ , g/sm ³	R(I) _a , nm	R(I) _c , nm	γ_a , mJ/m ²	γ_c , mJ/m ²
Gr	12,0	2,26	0,900 (3)	2,46 (3)	2195	130
G	12,0	2,26	0,246 (1)	-	2652	-
GrO	72,0	2,42	1,870 (3)	5,11 (3)	1931	85
GO	72,0	2,42	0,412 (1)	-	1311	-

From Table 1 it follows that the thickness of the surface layer of all graphene structures does not exceed 10 nm, i.e. they represent a nanostructure, at least in the z plane (Fig. 11a). Graphite and graphite oxide have 3 graphene monolayers each (Fig. 13), which confirms model (1) and Table 1..

Figure 13. – Change in graphene parameters depending on the number of layers (a) [21, 22]; graphene oxide CRS depending on the number of layers (b) [5, 6]

The first monolayer of graphite is graphene, it is determined by the unique physicochemical properties of graphene, such as a large theoretical specific surface area (~ 2600 m²/g), charge carrier mobility (~ 200,000 cm²/V•s), high Young's modulus (~ 1000 GPa), thermal conductivity (~ 5000 W/m K), optical transparency (~ 97.7%), mechanical strength, etc. [21, 23].

Bilayer graphene differs from single-layer graphene and graphite. It is studied [24] due to the controlled band gap. An analogue of bilayer graphene is SW graphene, which is more stable than graphene [25]. Three-layer graphene differs from the latter two in its mobility and conductivity [26]. The peculiarity of three-layer graphene is that after it is twisted at a magic angle, it develops superconductivity, which withstands magnetic fields 2-3 times greater than the Pauli limit for spin-singlet pairing [27].

In [28], superlattices based on single-layer and double-layer graphene are considered. They are actively studied for use in optoelectronics, acoustics, nanoplasmonics, etc. The author of [28] showed that based on the analysis of the dispersion equations of a superlattice consisting of alternating strips of single-layer and double-layer graphene, the parameters of the energy spectrum of which can be controlled by changing the external electric field perpendicular to the surface of the sample, obtained using the Kronig-Penny model, it is shown that the energy spectrum of such a superlattice can be approximated by the Kane model. The absorption coefficient of light during interband transitions in such a structure is calculated. In [29], a method is proposed for obtaining single-layer graphene oxide films of a large area on the surface of semiconductor silicon substrates by deposition from aqueous

suspensions. Graphene oxide is synthesized from natural crystalline graphite in the process of chemical oxidation and is a wide-bandgap dielectric material.

In [30], the change in the interlayer distance in a thin film consisting of two-layer graphene oxide under the action of water vapor and liquid water was studied

using atomic force microscopy. It was found that with an increase in the partial pressure of water vapor, the interlayer distance gradually increases and at a humidity of 80% reaches 1 nm. Three-layer graphene oxide differs from the latter two in the temperature dependence of the Raman spectra [5] (Fig. 14).

Figure 14. - Spectral position and FWHM of peaks D depending on temperature [5].

Using (2-5), we determine the elastic properties (Table 2).

Table 2.

Elastic parameters of graphene structures

Carbon	$W_{aa}, J/m^2$	$W_{ac}, J/m^2$	E_{da}, eV	E_{dc}, eV
Gr	2,853	1,690	2,27 (547 nm)	1,42
G	5,304	-	2,00 (620 nm)	-
GrO	2, 897	1,757	2,91 (427 nm)	1,82
GO	2,588	-	2,59 (477 nm)	-

According to the work [31], the deformation energy under external influence is spent on heat, acoustic emission, field emission and luminescence. Let us consider the luminescence of graphene structures. Let us compare the results obtained in Table 2 with the experimental values obtained in various works. Let us start

with the work [32], where the IR laser-induced radiation of carbon materials was experimentally studied. Broadband emission spectra were found in the visible region of the spectrum (Fig. 15).

Figure 15. - Emission spectra of carbon materials: massive polycrystalline graphite (1) and carbon black (2) in vacuum (a) and in air (b) [32]

From Figure 15, one can see a large coincidence of the spectra for graphite. We did not find any literary sources on graphene's luminescence. Let us compare Table 2 with the visible range (Figure 16).

VISIBLE SPECTRUM

Figure 16. – Visible wavelength range

From Table 2 and Figure 16 it is clear that graphene luminescence falls into an inconvenient region on the edge of IR radiation (invisible light), while for graphite it falls into the green glow region.

quite intense blue emission (Fig. 17). Blue emission from graphene oxide-based materials can be combined with yellow emission from materials such as ZnO to produce white light sources.

In [33], it was shown that acid-treated graphene samples, as well as reduced graphene oxide, exhibit

Figure 17. - Luminescence spectra of graphite oxide (FEG) and graphene oxide (FHG) [33]

From Fig. 17 and Table 2 and Fig. 16, their coincidence in the blue region is visible. In aqueous solutions, the luminescence of graphene oxide flakes is shown in Fig. 18.

Figure 18. – Luminescence spectra of graphene oxide flakes at different excitation energies (a); and at different PH values (b) [34]

From Fig. 18 it is evident that the luminescence spectra of graphene oxide flakes shift to the red region.

Conclusion

Comparison of the graphene structures Gr, G, GrO, GO (Tables 1 and 2) showed their insignificant difference from the unique properties of the original graphene. However, a significant difference of GO is the ability to vary the oxygen content by changing the physicochemical conditions of synthesis. At the same time, all parameters in Tables 1 and 2 can vary significantly. Further research is needed in this direction.

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